

iJERResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Dec, 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 27649733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10965794

NEUROSCIENCES IN EARLY CHILDHOOD

AUTHORS

- Cristiane Rosana da Silva
cristianerosana2009@gmail.com
- Marilia Monteiro Santos
marilia.monteiro@ymail.com

ABSTRACT:

Neuroscience is the field of science that seeks to study and understand the nervous system, with the aim of explaining the mechanisms that occur in the brain and their relationship with behavior and learning. In the child she is an important part of human development. The research is of a bibliographical nature, where the collected data are interpreted having as a source of investigation the knowledge derived from books and publications as well as electronic scientific bases. The formation of brain processes occurs from birth where all stimuli and experiences provided and experienced during this stage will directly influence the development of their brain skills. Favoring not only their cognitive capacity, but all the individual's abilities. We concluded, according to a study carried out, that the evolutionary capacity of the brain becomes slower over the years, since brain plasticity decreases with age.